

PRINCIPLES OF THE RIGHT TO EDUCATION AND SOCIAL SECURITY OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES.

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Abstract: Legal support of persons with disabilities is a priority and represents the social policy of the state and the system of measures to support them; aimed at creating equal opportunities for rehabilitation and ensuring participation in society

Key words: disabled people, education, rights and freedoms, social right, comfortable environment, values.

Persons with disabilities have the right to receive education in educational institutions of all levels and to participate in the life of society and the state throughout their lives in order to develop their abilities more fully. The state guarantees the development of inclusive education of persons with disabilities, the creation of the necessary conditions for their education and professional training, retraining and professional development. Educational organizations, together with state bodies, ensure that children with disabilities receive pre-school, out-of-school and general secondary education, as well as secondary special, professional, higher and post-higher education. If it is temporarily not possible to educate children with disabilities in educational institutions, state management bodies in the field of education and educational institutions based on the recommendations of doctors in the field of children with disabilities and the consent of their parents or other legal representatives provides education at home. Home education of children with disabilities is carried out at the expense of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The state guarantees that children with disabilities receive free general secondary, out-of-school, secondary special and professional education. Provision of special educational manuals and literature, as well as the services of sign language interpreters to persons with disabilities free of charge or on preferential terms, is carried out at the expense of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Non-governmental educational organizations have the right to set payment preferences for educating persons (children) with disabilities. Education of persons with disabilities, their vocational training, retraining and improvement of their qualifications in various forms, including separated from production and not separated from production, in the form of externships, as well as using distance learning technologies, in educational institutions of general type and organizations, in specialized educational institutions, at home, in special groups, in classes and by teaching according to individual curricula. In order to comprehensively and harmoniously develop children with disabilities, to form social activity in them, to arouse passion for work, to attract them to science, technology, art and sports, educational institutions organize extra-curricular activities for children with disabilities. must ensure the use of education, creating the necessary conditions for this, together with state bodies. Sign language is recognized by the Republic of Uzbekistan as a means of

interpersonal communication of persons with disabilities. Public authorities should develop languages, communication methods and tools that are more appropriate for each person with a disability, develop Braille, alternative letters, speech and oral communication skills, and include teachers and school staff. takes measures to improve the education system for persons with disabilities by providing training in educational matters, employing teachers with disabilities who know sign language and Braille in educational institutions. Social security mainly refers to provision and support of citizens through the state, state social security systems. But today, other forms of social security have begun to emerge. As for the concept of "social security right", this concept is directly related to the concept of "social security" and includes one aspect of it, i.e. the organizational and legal forms related to the implementation of social security, the legal system, reflects the system of state and, in appropriate cases, public bodies implementing social security. Due to the fact that social security is implemented from the state funds and by the authorized bodies of the state, the conditions and grounds for providing such security are determined imperatively by legal documents and are subject to the agreement of the recipient of social security and the body providing it. ra cannot be changed. During the regulation of relations related to non-state social protection, private legal methods may be allowed in accordance with the law, and its conditions may be determined and changed by agreement of the parties. The provisions of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights are reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the norms of national legislation that ensure reliable protection of political, economic, social and cultural rights and freedoms of a person. Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that everyone has the right to a standard of living necessary for the health and well-being of himself and his family, including clothing, food, medical care, and necessary social services. It is confirmed that he has the right to be provided for in the event of unemployment, illness, disability, widowhood, old age or other circumstances in which there are no means for living due to circumstances unrelated to it, and in which the social security all the main principles have been expressed. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws of our national legal system based on it, and other legal documents provide for the principles of social security. The principles of social security law consist of general legal principles and specific principles directly related to the implementation of various forms of social security.

The special principles of social security law include the following can include:

1. Generality and comprehensive nature of social security. It is understood that citizens receive social security on an equal basis, regardless of their nationality, gender, social status and other differences, if there are certain indicators. Suffice it to note that today about three and a half million citizens receive state pensions, hundreds of thousands of families and needy citizens receive allowances and other financial assistance, and for these purposes huge financial resources are spent from the state budget.

2. Targeted and specific orientation of social protection and non-adherence to neglect. Social protection measures for those who are unable to provide for themselves due to their health condition, age, family circumstances or other objective reasons, who are in need of state and community support and who are in need can be shown only to citizens and families who are found to be

3. Sufficient amount of funds allocated for social security. That is: the minimum amount of funds necessary for marriage at the time of determination of pensions and amounts, the

minimum level of funds necessary for the set of the most necessary products and services included in the consumer table e 'consideration is the essence of this principle. The minimum amounts of pensions, and their minimum amounts are determined by law and cannot be lower than this minimum amount, by periodically revising and indexing these minimum amounts. this principle is implemented. The principle of adequate social security is stipulated in article 11, paragraph 1 of the UN International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of December 19, 1966: and recognizes the right to an adequate standard of living, which includes adequate food, clothing and housing for his family, and the continuous improvement of his living conditions.

4. The principle of direct participation of citizens' self-management bodies, enterprises and organizations, and public associations in the implementation of social security. One of the manifestations of the fact that civil society is being established in our country, and that it is developing from a strong state to a strong society, is that the functions specific to the state are being transferred to society, and the tasks previously performed by state bodies are gradually being assigned to citizens' assemblies and other public bodies. is noticeable. Today, enterprises and organizations, their labor teams, various non-governmental foundations, charitable organizations, entrepreneurial citizens and other individuals are participating in the implementation of social security. It is predicted that this trend will continue to grow. Therefore, showing mercy to the weak, extending a helping hand, generosity, and tolerance are the national characteristics of the Uzbek people and are considered among our priceless traditions and ancient values that have been passed down from generation to generation.

5. The principle of implementation of social security in our country in various forms. In the legal documents on social security, provision is provided in various forms, in particular, in the form of pensions, one-time financial assistance, provision of social services, certain benefits and reliefs. In the future, it is expected that the forms of social assistance will become more diversified and perfected. The question of which form of social security is implemented is determined by legal documents, taking into account specific conditions. There is no doubt that the main form of social security is the provision of pensions, and it is clear that these two forms of social security will maintain their leading position, but it is natural that the form of pension will also be improved.

6. The principle of the state's comprehensive encouragement and support of the implementation of social security at the expense of non-state, sponsors' funds. Usually, citizens do not pay contributions for social security in advance (except for the cases provided for by law, citizens who are sole entrepreneurs and members of farmers) and social security budget funds, from the budget is carried out at the expense of the funds of the pension fund.

7. The principle of establishing state and public control over the implementation of social security. To ensure timely and full payment of social security funds, appropriate and correct spending, general control over the legality of activities of state and public bodies implementing social security, and their officials. It is carried out by the prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The education and social support of our vocational school students is carried out in accordance with the norms set by our state.

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